

Jewish Identity and Trauma in Jonathan Safran Foer's Work "Here I Am"

Dabbeta Ramesh

Research Scholar (Ph. D)

Department of English

Osmania University

Abstract:

*This article examines Jonathan Safran Foer's exploration of Jewish identity and trauma through his novels *Everything Is Illuminated* (2002), *Extremely Loud and Incredibly Close* (2005), and *Here I Am* (2016). Foer, a prominent American Jewish writer often associated with the third generation of Holocaust literature, intricately weaves themes of Jewish identity and historical trauma into his works. This study investigates how Foer's narratives address the transmission of Holocaust experiences across generations, the impact of contemporary traumas like 9/11, and the complex dynamics of Jewish identity within the context of American and Israeli perspectives. By analysing Foer's literary techniques and thematic concerns, this article sheds light on the challenges faced by Jewish characters in reconciling their personal and collective histories with their present realities.*

Keywords: Jewish identity, Holocaust literature, American Jewish fiction, trauma, generational transmission, Israeli-American relations

Introduction

While numerous Jewish-American writers have explored themes pertaining to Jewish identity in their books, only a small number have directly engaged in this particular argument. Nevertheless, there has been a noticeable surge of interest in Israel in recent American Jewish literature. Jonathan Safran Foer examines the predicaments encountered by American Jews in his book *Here I Am* (2016). Jonathan Safran Foer, an American Jewish novelist frequently categorised as a member of the third-generation Holocaust writers, has demonstrated a significant fascination with Jewish identity in his literary works. The debut novel, *Everything is Illuminated* (2002), explores the transmission of Holocaust tragedy across generations. The story is structured into two distinct narratives. One of these narratives focusses on the protagonist's family in Trachimbrod, a Jewish shtetl. The alternate account chronicles his expedition to Trachimbrod, motivated by the desire to locate the woman credited with rescuing his grandfather during the battle. Codde interprets the novel as an endeavour to "gain entry,

recreate, and artistically depict (or 're-present') a traumatic past that is inherently unattainable" (62). In his second work of fiction, titled *Extremely Loud and Incredibly Close* (2005), Foer explores the topic of the 9/11 attacks, as well as several other types of trauma. He delves into the ways in which languages may effectively convey experiences of suffering and memories. His latest literary creation, *Here I Am*, can be considered as his most quintessentially Jewish piece of writing. Furthermore, he explores several aspects of Jewish identity, in addition to illustrating the enduring impact of the Holocaust horror on Jewish characters. The novel illustrates the challenges faced by younger American Jews in defining their Jewish identity due to divergent interpretations of Jewishness between elder generations of their family and the Israeli Jewish community.

In *Here I Am*, Foer explores the connection between American Jews and Israel. Foer's *Here I Am* explores the various approaches that Foer employed to include Israel into the narrative, despite the plot mostly taking place in America. The tale highlights the contrasting characteristics of American and Israeli Jews, whose Jewish ancestry seems to have developed divergently. Foer's protagonist Jacob endeavours to reconstruct the various ideals and Jewish aspects that he deems significant. The discussion shifts to Foer's portrayal of Israel after analysing the representation of Jacob's Jewish identity in the novel.

Here I Am challenges the notion that Israel is the definitive Jewish homeland, as the characters exemplify that Jewish individuals can establish a sense of belonging in many nations. Additionally, the protagonist openly expresses his opinions towards Israel and voices criticism towards the actions of Prime Minister Netanyahu. In the article "Jonathan Safran Foer: My Israeli friends want to raise kids elsewhere" published by Jewish Telegraphic Agency, it is stated that Foer holds the belief that Israel, under Netanyahu's leadership, has distanced itself from the rest of the Western world. This has resulted in academic boycotts and other consequences. The author highlighted that as a consequence, numerous of his Israeli acquaintances are no longer inclined to raise their children in Israel and are growing weary of residing there. According to his statement, Israelis possess a deep affection for their nation and are willing to make the ultimate sacrifice for it. However, they no longer desire for their offspring to be raised within its borders. Foer stated that if Israel adopts a more fundamentalist approach, similar to its neighbouring countries, it will jeopardise the cherished aspiration of many Jews to form and maintain the State of Israel.

Here I Am chronicles the experiences of the Blochs, an American Jewish family residing in Washington D.C., for a period of up to six weeks, during which they encounter two distinct crises. The first crisis is to home affairs, specifically the potential divorce between Jacob and his wife Julia. The second crisis occurs in Israel, where a severe earthquake strikes the Middle East. This situation initially stems from geological factors, but subsequently evolves into a political issue, ultimately posing a significant threat to the existence of Israel. Amidst these catastrophes, the characters are consistently confronted with obligations and predicaments, necessitating them to make crucial choices.

While both *Here I Am* and Philip Roth's work explore comparable issues, Foer employs different tactics than Roth to establish Israel in his story. The work distinguishes itself from the literary convention of American Jewish characters embarking on a pilgrimage to Israel in pursuit of purpose and self-discovery. Foer explores several approaches to examine the perspectives of American Jewish characters on Israel and their obligations and commitments to it, all within the confines of the United States.

Flashbacks are employed to introduce Israel. Several recollections shed light on the fragmentation of one's family following the Holocaust, as one faction of the family opted to relocate to America while the other chose Israel. In addition, the narrative underscores the fact that Jacob and his sons are likewise inclined towards engaging in discussions regarding Israeli matters. Consequently, Israel is occasionally brought up in the Blochs' family conversations. Foer presents a dystopian narrative by depicting the imminent destruction of Israel in a menacing manner. The reader is cognisant of Israel's predicament since the inception of the narrative, as the narrator explicitly states in the opening sentence. The geological crisis rapidly escalates into a political crisis, pitting Israel against its bordering countries.

While Foer initially adopts a more realistic style and explores household themes, he ultimately returns to the post-modern tradition that characterised his two previous fictional works. Similar to Foer's previous works, *Everything is Illuminated* and *Extremely Loud and Incredibly Close*, his third novel also employs a fragmented narrative style. According to Menaker, the novel *Here I Am* by Foer follows a similar narrative style as his previous two post-modernist novels. These novels also included a mixture of contradicting stories and additional narrative documents. The various components stated earlier, including distinct narratives, supplementary narrative materials, flashbacks, interior monologues, dialogues,

virtual games, and text messages, are unified through the implementation of a literary technique known as montage. The novel incorporates several elements such as virtual dialogues, family discussions, multiple accounts, extra narrative documents, text messages, flashbacks, and interior monologues, which all intertwine with each other.

To summarise, while Roth focusses on Israel and its setting, Foer explores the topic of Israel without actually shifting the narrative to that location. He accomplishes this through the utilisation of several literary techniques, including metaphors, dialogues, the incorporation of news items, text messages, chats, interviews, flashbacks, and a dystopian storyline. The combination of all these aspects is achieved through the implementation of a literary technique known as montage. Foer is able to mitigate the conflict between seemingly contradictory components, such as Jacob's familial issues and the Israeli predicament. Foer's story blurs the distinction between its various narratives, so causing the reader to continually contemplate Israel and the ongoing events in the Middle East.

Foer, like to Isaac, reinforces the distinctiveness of Jewish existence in America. Scott contends that the label "counter-Zionist" is more appropriate for *Here I Am*, as opposed to "anti-Zionist". This statement implies that, similar to Operation Shylock but with even greater emphasis, it identifies a credible form of counter-Zionism inside the American Jewish experience. Foer, the author, does not consider this alternative Jewish identity to be any less genuine or courageous than the Israeli version. The novel illustrates that it is possible to lead a meaningful Jewish existence without possessing exceptional physical strength, virility, or heroism, but rather by fulfilling one's familial obligations. Scott characterises *Here I Am* as a fervent ode to contentment, an excessively ambitious justification of humility and prudence, and a grandiose tribute to the insignificance of existence.

In the novel *Here I Am*, the Israeli characters' residences vividly portray the heightened vitality of life in Israel in contrast to that of America. This exemplifies the reality that Israelis are regularly confronted with significant news and visuals that may be emotionally challenging to witness. Foer's work portrays television as a form of entertainment in America, serving as a diversion from more significant aspects of life, such as education or family.

The narrative juxtaposes the potential annihilation of the motherland with the domestic difficulties faced by Jacob and Julia. Both the war and the divorce can be interpreted as a

symbolic representation of each other. Foer underscores this analogy by use military terminology to depict the dissolution of Jacob and Julia's marriage.

Here I Am, while exploring various other issues, is a novel that examines the subject of Jewish Diaspora and the notions of home and homeland. The characters' fragmented identity is further exacerbated by the divergence in conceptions of Jewishness among other Jewish individuals. According to certain Jewish individuals, Israel is regarded as the authentic Jewish homeland, while the residence of the Blochs is in America.

Foer characterised his Israeli acquaintances as individuals who possess a deep affection for their homeland and are willing to make the ultimate sacrifice for it. However, they no longer desire to bring up their children in that particular country. Curiously, this is the manner in which Tamir is shown in the novel *Here I Am*. Despite his efforts to enhance his house, he ultimately acknowledges his intention to relocate to America. He contemplates creating "hayila," which is the antithesis of Aliyah. The number is 413. This elucidates the reason why, notwithstanding the abhorrent occurrences transpiring in his homeland, he persisted in relishing the sightseeing destinations in his relatives' urban centre. Throughout that entire duration, he was actively searching for a new residence in a more secure location.

Undoubtedly, Tamir possesses a deep affection for his country and actively engages in combat when war erupts. However, he holds the belief that this location is not conducive for raising his children. His want to go from Israel becomes evident when his son becomes obligated to enlist in the military, and intensifies further when his son is deployed to the West Bank. Noam, residing in Israel, appears to be lacking the typical lifestyle that is expected for someone of his age to relish. During their conversation about his future intentions, he informs Sam that up until now, he has been unable to derive pleasure from life, stating,

"After my military service, it's been all about school." Life after school. I am optimistic.
(363)

In *Here I Am*, it is concluded that material features alone are insufficient to create a truly exceptional home and land. Other factors, such as hospitality and safety, are seen more significant.

Although Foer asserts that he does not intend to advocate for any specific political perspective, his novel effectively articulates the concerns experienced by American Jews,

particularly in relation to Israel. The portrayal illustrates the progressive alienation of American Jews from the State, prompting them to rethink their Jewish identity. Furthermore, the novel delves into a catastrophic situation unfolding in the Middle East, which mirrors the apprehension felt by Jewish individuals due to Israel's encirclement by multiple conflicts and adversaries.

Foer demonstrates that Israel's political actions have the potential to exacerbate the already strained relationship between American Jews and the State of Israel. In the book *Here I Am*, the Israeli government demonstrates callous behaviour towards its neighbouring countries throughout the crisis, thus disregarding fundamental principles of American Jewish culture. As a result, after the conflict ends, the American Jewish characters have an increased sense of separation from both the State and Israeli Jews.

Here I Am illustrates the significant influence of the media on the connection between Diasporic Jews and Israel, as it serves as the primary conduit of information regarding the ongoing events in the region. With the exception of a few visits to their relatives' residence, the Blochs have minimal personal interaction with Israel and primarily acquire information about it through online sources, television, and newspapers.

Jonathan Safran Foer is the inaugural prominent American Jewish writer to portray the annihilation of Israel, and the situation he envisions is highly credible. The reasons provided by Foer's character, the Israeli engineer, are grounded in factual evidence. Foer's unwavering commitment to setting the story in America, together with his persistent exploration of Jacob's struggle with his sense of self, indicates that his intention is not simply to offer criticism of Israel, but also to examine the State's connection with American Jews. In *Here I Am*, the author illustrates the existing gap between American Jews and Israel and examines the potential for their relationship to worsen if the Israeli government continues to make decisions that contravene their shared principles. The work initially emphasises the disparity between American Jews and Israel through the portrayal of Jacob and Tamir's complex relationship, which encompasses elements of rivalry, animosity, and emotional detachment.

In addition, Foer illustrates that the connection between American Jews and Israel may continue to worsen. The author introduces the dystopian narrative to communicate a crucial warning and to examine Israel's potential response to crisis situations. The aftermath of the earthquake might be seen as a critique of Israel's prioritisation on military security, which has

resulted in the neglect of other crucial aspects. These factors encompass several aspects, such as the implementation of a suitable architectural code, as well as some Jewish principles like righteousness.

In the novel *Here I Am*, the Israeli government has made ethically dubious choices in order to safeguard its sovereignty.

Similar to the protagonist in *Everything is Illuminated*, the main character in this story also comes from a lineage of third-generation Holocaust survivors. Isaac, the grandpa, is a survivor of the Holocaust and has had certain PTSD symptoms. The survivor of the Holocaust, he was profoundly impacted by the stark reality that he and Benny were the sole members of their family to endure the atrocities. The Holocaust continues to be a fundamental aspect of identification for every generation in the Blochs' family. Foer posits that the Jewish community has cultivated a persistent apprehension of outsiders and an intense preoccupation with self-preservation due to their inability to surmount the anguish inflicted by the tragic events they underwent, notably the Holocaust. Instead of expressing a forward-looking perspective by proclaiming *Here I Am*, they persistently dwell on the events that transpired in their community in the past.

The work does not aim to prove that American Jews completely lack support for Israel, but rather challenges their allegiance. Due to Israel not being their place of residence, it inevitably feels distant to some individuals. Furthermore, if Israel behaves in a manner that contradicts American principles, such as democracy, it is highly probable that this emotional detachment will intensify even more.

Foer's work *Here I Am* transcends being a mere narrative of midlife crises and divorce. The text delves into the concerns and apprehensions around Jewish identity and the state of Israel among American Jews in contemporary culture. *Here I Am* emphasises the profound division within the modern Jewish community. In Foer's story, American Jewish individuals have a profound sense of conflict and division as a consequence of their multiple identities. Since Isaac immigrated to America, the Blochs have assimilated into their new country, cultivated a feeling of American identity, and the subsequent generations have embraced secularism. As a result, Jacob's understanding of Jewish identity is distinct from that of previous generations, and he feels compelled to reconstruct the Jewish traditions and ideals that he wishes to uphold. The work reiterates the significance of rites and ceremonies, and more

notably, serves as a reminder to readers about the necessity of righteousness as a core Jewish principle. The challenge of upholding Jewish identity in a secular society has been explored in various American Jewish literary works. However, Foer highlights an additional dimension of the American Jews' divided sense of self by presenting his characters with encounters with Israeli Jews.

Foer's story emphasises the varying interpretations of Jewishness within different Jewish groups. Foer's portrayal of Israeli and American individuals suggests that he saw the Jewish legacy as having diverged, with each group exhibiting distinct ideals. Due to the prominent role of the army in Israeli society, military values have had a significant impact on Israeli Jews. Therefore, according to Foer's portrayal of Israeli characters, being Jewish encompasses qualities of heroism, strength, and virility. Additionally, it entails military service and a commitment to defending their homeland's political existence. In contrast, Jacob's family members do not share the same connection with the army and have embraced more progressive ideas that are typical of America. The narrative accentuates the disparity in ideals by underscoring the physical dissimilarities between the Israeli characters, who are portrayed as more robust and vigorous, and the Blochs.

The novel portrays family as the fundamental element of Jewish existence. Hence, Foer arrives to the inference that one's home is not determined by nationality, culture, or religion, but rather by family. Initially, Jacob displays feelings of envy towards what he believes to be a vibrant and fulfilling life in Israel. He expresses dissatisfaction with his own mundane existence as a father and husband, referring to it as the "Great Flatness". However, he eventually comes to the realisation that America is where he truly belongs. By bestowing his novel with the title *Here I Am* and employing this quotation frequently, Foer reaffirms the status of his American Jewish protagonists within the Diaspora. Using the character Sam, Foer revisits the original biblical significance of the phrase "Here I am" and incorporates it into his narrative. Sam clarifies that Abraham's response of "Here I am" demonstrates his unwavering dedication, as it signifies his complete presence and readiness for both God and his son. In the end, Jacob concludes that his utmost desire is to be fully attentive and devoted to his family, the entity to whom he wishes to proclaim his unwavering presence. Hence, "there he is", residing in the Diaspora.

Foer effectively establishes a connection between the home and dystopian components of the novel through the utilisation of various literary approaches. Jacob's midlife crisis mirrors the broader Jewish identity issue. He strongly condemns his persistent lack of resolve and grapples with the challenge of making choices. This exemplifies the increasing ambiguity around Jewish identity and cohesion among the Jewish community. Foer establishes a connection between the divorce and the destruction of Israel through the utilisation of metaphors and montages. Despite appearing as distinct experiences, these events exhibit numerous similarities. Indeed, the challenges faced by the couple and the downfall of Israel might be attributed to a growing separation between Jacob and Julia, as well as between American and Israeli Jews. Jacob's divorce and midlife crisis prompt him to reflect on his role as a husband and father, while the ongoing crisis in Israel leads him to doubt his Jewish identity, specifically his loyalty to the State. In addition, similar to the portrayal of the Jewish community in the novel, Jacob and Julia are fixated on the past and struggle to escape their traumatic experiences. Both scenarios result in the destruction of dwellings. Jacob is forced to leave his home due to his divorce, while Israeli buildings collapse as a consequence of the earthquake. In addition, Israel does not provide a sense of belonging for the American Jewish personalities.

In *Here I Am*, Foer expresses a strong pessimism on the future of the relationship between American Jews and Israel. Nevertheless, one may contend that he holds a notably positive outlook regarding the future of the Diasporic Jewish community. Indeed, his characters exemplify the ability of Jewish individuals to assimilate into their new nations and integrate into the global society while still maintaining their Jewish identity. Despite undergoing assimilation, the younger generations nevertheless experience a strong sense of affiliation with the Jewish community. Foer illustrates that the Jewish identity can be reconfigured to better align with their new lives and views. The statement *Here I am* asserts that the American Jewish characters are part of the Diaspora and have made a deliberate choice to continue living there.

In addition, the Israelis are depicted as individuals who prioritise their possessions, and Israel is depicted as a nation that places emphasis on its survival and the rapid construction of settlements. The narrative emphasises that by prioritising those characteristics, the State has neglected several significant factors. Ultimately, the Israeli individuals experience a sense of dissatisfaction in their native nation due to the unfriendly conditions prevailing in their country, which perpetually instills anxiety for the safety of their children. The dystopian plot in *Here I*

Am is around a violent earthquake that triggers a geographical and political catastrophe in Israel. This plot emphasises that Israelis have been constructing numerous dwellings in their land, but they have done so incorrectly. Technically speaking, this indicates that they have allocated significant resources towards constructing settlements, but their emphasis has been on swift growth rather than adhering to building regulations. Consequently, the Israeli homes crumble when the earthquake strikes the Middle East. Figuratively, this suggests that their attention has been directed towards materialistic concerns and military defence rather than fostering a welcoming environment. As a result, the Israeli residences have not succeeded in becoming genuine homes.

Foer also articulates concerns and apprehensions arising from the State's geopolitical position in the Middle East. Israel's primary objective is to provide a secure haven for Jews, but it has consistently been embroiled in ongoing and intense violent battles since its establishment. The tale highlights the lack of safety in Israel by vividly describing Tamir's dwelling and his anxious expressions on his family's living conditions. Furthermore, due to its distressing history, the Jewish community is portrayed as harbouring apprehensions that other nations, especially America, could fail to support them during a crisis, as they have previously done. Regarding American Jews alone, Foer emphasises their fear of being exploited by both Israeli and American media and politicians. In the United States, they lack authority over the situation in Israel and heavily rely on the news to stay updated on the events unfolding in the Middle East, thereby granting significant influence to the media.

Foer portrays the challenge of navigating dual Jewish and American identities, while emphasising that American Jewish characters experience a sense of conflict due to the deep divisions among the Jewish community, particularly when contrasting Israel with America. This study has also emphasised how Foer portrays the distinctions between those two Jewish groups. Halevi contends that recognising and addressing the distinctions and commonalities between American and Israeli Jews will contribute to the growth and resilience of both communities (Kuruvilla).

References

Goldberg, Jeffrey. "The American Jewish-Israeli Jewish Divorce Seems to Be Inching Close. Neither Side Has a Full Understanding of the Other. Geography May Be Destiny."

Twitter, 14 May 2018, 8:22 p.m.,
twitter.com/JeffreyGoldberg/status/996229414265540610.

“A Portrait of Jewish Americans.” *Pew Research Center*, 1 Oct. 2013,
www.pewforum.org/2013/10/01/jewish-american-beliefs-attitudes-culture-survey/.
Accessed 21 Apr. 2018.

“Diaspora.” *Oxford Dictionaries*, en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/diaspora. Accessed 25
Apr. 2018.

Foer, Jonathan Safran. *Here I Am*. Penguin, 2016.

“Jonathan Safran Foer: ‘Here I Am: A Novel’ | Talks at Google.” *YouTube*, uploaded by Talks
at Google, 13 July 2017, www.youtube.com/watch?v=N1XEQ3jhsSA.